

Effect of Innovative Behavior, Interpersonal Communication, Principal Managerial Competence on School Organization Development

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to see whether there is an influence of innovative behavior, interpersonal communication, managerial competence, and organizational development on the performance of the Principal of Primary Schools in Labuhanbatu Regency. The population in this study was the principal of the State Elementary School in Labuhanbatu Regency as many as 241 schools. To determine the number of research samples, using the Isaac and Michael Tables at a significance level of 5 percent. Based on the table, for a population of 241, a sample of 142 was obtained. Data collection instruments used questionnaires and observation sheets which were adapted from the Ministry of National Education. Data analysis using SPSS dIn the analysis conducted, GOF measurement can be seen from the main measurement triangle, namely Chi-square value, calculated P-value, and RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) 1) Innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the managerial competence of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the SD principal's innovative behavior, the better the SDSD managerial competence in Labuhanbatu Regency, 2) Innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the performance of the SD principal in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the innovative behavior, the better the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency, 3) Innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the development of elementary school organization in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the innovative behavior, the

higher the development of the headmaster's organization in Labuhanbatu Regency, 4) Interpersonal communication has a direct positive effect on the managerial competence of elementary school heads in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better interpersonal communication, the better the managerial competence of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency, 5) Interpersonal communication has a direct positive effect on the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better interpersonal communication, the better the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency, 6) Interpersonal Communication has a direct positive effect on the development of elementary school organization in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better interpersonal communication, the better the development of the organization of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency, 7) Managerial competence has a direct positive effect on the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better the managerial competency of the SD Principal, the better the SD Principal's performance in Labuhanbatu Regency, 8) Organizational development has a positive direct effect on the SD Principal's performance in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the ability to develop an SD principal's organization, the better the SD principal's performance in Labuhanbatu Regency.

Keywords: Innovative Behavior, Interpersonal Communication, Managerial Competence, Organizational Development, Principal Performance.

INTRODUCTION

According to Mulyasa, the School Principal is one of the most important educational components in improving the quality of education, because the school principal is the manager of education at the education unit or the school level. Therefore, the principal is responsible for the back and forth of the school. Based on this, a school principal should have the ability and skills to support the achievement of his performance as a school principal. The amount of workload can be completed by the principal and can even result in good work performance if the principal has the ability and skills that can support the success of the principal in carrying out the task. The ability and skills in question are the ability of principals to conduct innovative behavior, interpersonal communication skills, managerial abilities, and the ability to carry out organizational development. These four abilities and skills will support a school principal to be able to display maximum performance (Aisyah et al, 2016)¹.

Principals are expected to have the ability to: create innovations that are useful for school development; work hard to achieve school success as an effective learning organization; have a strong motivation to succeed in carrying out their main duties and functions as school leaders; never give up and always look for the best solution in facing obstacles faced by schools; have an entrepreneurial instinct in managing school activities as a source of learning for students (Manap et al, 2010)⁷.

In addition to being able to behave innovatively, principals should also have skills in applying management systems and creative leadership. Creative management and expertise looking for concrete solutions to problems needed by a school principal. For this reason, every leader of an educational institution, in this case, the principal, is demanded to be able to be creative, innovative, to improve the quality of learning, curriculum development, teacher quality development, financing

improvement, provision of facilities and infrastructure, and also fostering the personality and skills of students (Darmada, 2013)³.

In addition to funding problems that make it difficult for school principals to include themselves as well as teachers or students under the organization they lead, information is often not up to or even late from the District Education Office. The school principals stated that they were often late in getting training information relating to the development of principals' competencies. Generally, the type of training that is followed is the application of K13 in schools such as filling out report cards, compiling curriculum, conducting supervision, and others. Principals, especially private schools, need training related to improving basic competencies that must be possessed by school principals because they are generally appointed not based on the appointment system using the AKPK test. The appointment is more for the election made by the foundation as the owner so that rarely follows training related to the basic competency of a school principal. Besides, if the principal has attended training, often other problems arise because the principal is unable to deliver or apply the results of the training he has attended. Another problem faced by school principals is the frequency with which commands or instructions are delivered are not obeyed or tend to appear to be ignored by teachers, especially teachers who are already senior compared to him.

Problems in getting information late or inability to give instructions or orders to subordinates are bad evidence of the inability of principals to interpersonal communication both to superiors, colleagues, subordinates, and to stakeholders. Humans in their lives must communicate, meaning that they need other people and need groups or communities to interact with each other. Syarif (2011:128)¹² states that school principals need to have the ability to communicate important matters to create a conducive and dynamic working

atmosphere.

LITERATUR REVIEW

Interpersonal communication is one of the most effective ways of changing attitudes, beliefs, opinions, and communicant behavior, so this form of interpersonal communication is often used to convey persuasive communication, which is a psychologically human communication technique that is subtle, flexible in the form of solicitation, persuasion or seduction. With so then every communicator will perform four actions is to establish, deliver, receive and process the message, the fourth such action takes place sequentially and form a message which is defined as creating an idea or ideas for specific purposes.

According to Siswandi (Krismastyanti, 2013)⁶, School principals have a very strong role in coordinating, mobilizing, and harmonizing all available educational resources in schools. The ability of the principal to lead the school in realizing the vision and mission, goals, and objectives of the school through programs that are planned. Principals are also required to have adequate managerial skills to be able to take initiatives and initiatives to improve the quality of schools.

In running a school organization a principal must be able to drive and run his organization, in the sense that the principal must be able to bring change because change is the main goal of leadership. An important step for implementing change is to strengthen innovative behavior for members, groups, and the organization itself. Organizational development in principle is a process whereby knowledge, concepts, and practices related to organizational behavior are used effectively to assist the organization in achieving its objectives. This process also includes how to improve the quality of organizational performance and at the same time increase the productivity (members) of the organization.

To carry out programs that have been planned and to overcome obstacles that

occur during the process of organizational development, a strategy and method are needed. One way that can be done is by lobbying and negotiating. For an organization, lobbying is necessary for successful implementation of plans and negotiation is reciprocal communication designed to achieve a common goal. For example, lobbying for CSR funds from companies, negotiating with leaders and subordinates, and so forth. For lobbying and negotiations to run smoothly and produce agreements, interpersonal communication skills are needed. Where interpersonal communication is communication that can convince, influence, and ultimately change the attitude of the communicant or interlocutor to want to follow the communicator's will, therefore the principal must master interpersonal communication. Based on the above, in this study, the proposed title is the Effect of Innovative Behavior, Interpersonal Communication, Managerial Competence, and Organizational Development on the Performance of Primary School Principals in Labuhanbatu Regency.

METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out in Labuhanbatu Regency for 6 (six) months from July 2019 to December 2019. The target population in this study was the principal of the State Primary Schools in Labuhanbatu Regency as many as 241 schools. The research sample was taken as part of the target population of each sub-district, taking into account the length of service of office, education, and rank. To determine the number of research samples, using the Isaac and Michael Tables at a significance level of 5 percent. Based on the table, for a population of 241, a sample of 142 was obtained. The sampling technique used was Proportional Random Sampling, which is a simple random sampling proportionally based on districts.

Table 1 Distribution of Principals for Each District as Population and Sample

No	Nama Kecamatan	Jumlah kepala sekolah (sebagai Populasi)	Jumlah kepala sekolah (sebagai Sampel)
1	Rantau Utara	25	15
2	Bilah Hulu	45	26
3	Panai Tengah	23	14
4	Panai Hilir	23	14
5	Bilah Barat	29	17
6	Bilah Hilir	29	17
7	Rantau Selatan	19	11
8	Pangkatan	26	15
9	Panai Hulu	22	13
Jumlah		241	142

Source: Dapo.dikdasmen.kemdikbud.go.id id for the odd semester 2019/2020

There are 5 five variables involved in this study, namely exogenous variables, in this case, are Innovative Behavior and Interpersonal communication from the principal. Performance, Organizational Development, and Managerial Competence of school principals are endogenous variables. The data collection tool or data instrument used is a questionnaire that was developed by the researcher himself. Performance data were collected by assessing the performance of primary school principals in Labuhanbatu District, using a performance assessment sheet from the Ministry of National Education. Managerial competency data is collected by making observations using an observation sheet for managerial competency evaluation for

school principals from the Ministry of National Education. Data on innovative behavior, interpersonal communication skills, and the development of the principal's organization was collected by distributing questionnaires to the principal of the primary school in Labuhanbatu Regency. All data collected are then tabulated for further analysis. The requirements tested for path analysis, in this case, are data normality, data linearity, and multicollinearity between predictor variables (Surjana, 2013)⁸. At this test stage, the Lisrel 10.1 program is used, in the analysis conducted, the GOF size can be seen from the main size triangle, namely Chi-square value, calculated P-value, and RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation).

RESULT

Testing Requirements Analysis

Table 2 Summary of the Kolmogorov- Smirnov Test Normality

No.	Variable	nilai Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) > 0,05	Information
1	Perilaku Inovatif	0.076	Normal
2	Komunikasi Interpersonal	0.132	Normal
3	Kompetensi Manajerial	0.097	Normal
4	Pengembangan Organisasi	0.066	Normal
5	Kinerja Kepsek	0.522	Normal

Table 3 Summary of Test Results from linearity and test thesignificance

No.	Exogenous Variables with respect to endogeneous Variables	Linearity Test			Test the significance of regresion		
		F _h	Sig.	Stat	F _h	Sig.	Status
1	X ₁ dengan X ₃	1.204	0.236	Linier	145.578	0,000	Signifikan
2	X ₂ dengan X ₃	1.382	,101	Linier	141.903	0,000	Signifikan
3	X ₁ dengan X ₄	1.427	,088	Linier	87.937	0,000	Signifikan
4	X ₃ dengan X ₄	1.071	,383	Linier	99.892	0,000	Signifikan
5	X ₁ dengan X ₅	,931	,581	Linier	188.687	0,000	Signifikan
6	X ₂ dengan X ₅	,899	,638	Linier	213.557	0,000	Signifikan
7	X ₃ dengan X ₅	1.093	,352	Linier	211.595	0,000	Signifikan
8	X ₄ dengan X ₅	1.162	,271	Linier	151.293	0,000	Significant

Table 4 Summary of Calculation of Correlation Coefficient , Path Coefficient and Meaning

Hypothesis Number	Coefficient Correlation*	Path Coefficient	t _{hitung}	Sig.	Information
1	$\Gamma_{13} = 0,714$	$\rho_{31} = 0,421$	5.345	0.000	Sig. < 0,05, Berarti
2	$\Gamma_{23} = 0,709$	$\rho_{32} = 0,405$	5.140	0.000	
3	$\Gamma_{14} = 0,621$	$\rho_{41} = 0,324$	3.612	0.000	
4	$\Gamma_{24} = 0,645$	$\rho_{43} = 0,411$	4.585	0.000	
5	$\Gamma_{15} = 0,758$	$\rho_{51} = 0,237$	3.480	0.001	
6	$\Gamma_{25} = 0,777$	$\rho_{52} = 0,294$	4.275	0.000	
7	$\Gamma_{35} = 0,776$	$\rho_{53} = 0,253$	3.519	0.001	
8	$\Gamma_{45} = 0,721$	$\rho_{54} = 0,205$	3.241	0.001	

Hypothesis test

(a) Hipotesis 1 dan 2

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,767 ^a	,588	,582	30,029

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	178926,478	2	89463,239	99,213	,000 ^b
	Residual	125340,741	139	901,732		
	Total	304267,218	141			

a. Dependent Variable: Kompetensi Manajerial
b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovative Behavior, Interpersonal Communication

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22,351	13,053		1,712	,089
	Komunikasi Interpersonal	1,424	,266	,421	5,345	,000
	Perilaku Inovatif	1,078	,210	,405	5,140	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Managerial Competence

Referring to the regression output above, thus obtained the path diagram of structure I model as follows:

Based on the diagram above, then to test the hypothesis:

1) Analysis of the effect of innovative behavior on the principal's managerial competence

From the above analysis innovative behavioral significance value $0.000 > 0.05$. So, it can be concluded that there is a direct influence of innovative behavior on the principal's managerial competence. Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, a significant path coefficient was obtained between Innovative Behavior and Managerial Competence, namely: $\rho_{31} = 0,421$. Furthermore, based on the calculation of proportional influences obtained by the direct influence of Innovative Behavior on Managerial Competence as large as 0,421. Thus, Innovative Behavior influences the direct positive effect on Managerial Competence, of which 42.10% of change Managerial competence can be

determined by Innovative Behavior. Accuracy of a person in school in understanding regulations certainly depends on how much information (knowledge) that is owned and of course the accuracy of the decision was taken, it depends on the level of knowledge of who owned. Because of this, the high level of Innovative Behavior that belongs to the schools makes it easier to understand the policies that are supported in the form of regulations. Based on this, it can be assumed that the level of Innovative Behavior of the school from the head of the school affects the Managerial Competence as positive and significant.

2) Analysis of the influence of interpersonal communication on managerial competence

From the above analysis results obtained significance value $0.000 > 0.05$. So, it can be concluded that there is a significant direct effect between interpersonal communication on the principal's managerial competence. Based on the results of the second hypothesis testing obtained a significant path coefficient between Interpersonal Communication with Managerial Competence, namely: $\rho_{32} = 0.405$. Furthermore, based on the results of the calculation of proportional effect obtained direct influence of Interpersonal Communication on Managerial Competence of 0.405. Thus, interpersonal

communication has a direct positive effect on managerial competence, which is 40.50%. Changes in Managerial Competence can be influenced by

Interpersonal Communication. Likewise, the interpersonal communication of the principal in his daily life affects both Managerial Competence and performance

(b) Hypothesis 3 and 4

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,683 ^a	,466	,459	14,257

Predictors: (Constant), Behavior Innovative Communications Interpersonal

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24702,401	2	12351,200	60,767	,000 ^b
	Residual	28252,395	139	203,255		
	Total	52954,796	141			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Development
b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovative Behavior, Interpersonal Communication

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	14,351	6,197		2,316	,022
	Komunikasi Interpersonal	,457	,126	,324	3,612	,000
	Perilaku Inovatif	,456	,100	,411	4,585	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Development

3) Analysis of the effect of innovative behavior on the development of the principal's organization

From the above analysis innovative behavioral significance value $0.000 > 0.05$. So, it can be concluded that there is a direct influence of innovative behavior on the development of school head organizations. The third hypothesis testing results obtained a significant path coefficient between Innovative Behavior with Organizational Development, namely: $\rho_{41} = 0.324$. Furthermore, based on the results of the calculation of proportional effect obtained direct influence of Innovative Behavior with Organizational Development of 0.324. Thus Innovative Behavior has a direct positive effect on Organizational Development, where 32.40% of changes in Organizational Development can be determined by Innovative Behavior. The ability to behave innovatively is a basic asset in having ideas

for developing organizational development strategies. Innovation is an idea, both from within and from outside oneself to create and implement a new one which will ultimately have a positive impact on the organization. Principals are expected to have the ability to: create innovations that are useful for school development; work hard to achieve school success as an effective learning organization; have a strong motivation to succeed in carrying out their main duties and functions as school leaders; never give up and always look for the best solution in facing obstacles faced by schools; have an entrepreneurial instinct in managing school activities as a source of learning for students.

4) Analysis of the effect of interpersonal communication on organizational development

From the above analysis results obtained significance value $0.000 > 0.05$. so it can be concluded that there is a significant direct effect between interpersonal communication on the development of the principal's organization. Furthermore, based on the calculation of the proportional effect obtained by the direct effect of interpersonal

communication on Organizational Development of 0.411. Thus interpersonal communication has a direct positive effect on Organizational Development, in which 41.10% changes in Organizational Development can be determined by interpersonal communication. For that, we need the same understanding between the two parties, namely superiors and subordinates. This can encourage enthusiasm and enthusiasm for work to be able to complete the tasks and responsibilities given meaning between

superiors and subordinates jointly issue ideas and implement these ideas to develop the organization for the realization of organizational goals. In its application, the school principal can do both formally and informally to obtain information or provide information. Interpersonal communication is related to the activity of delivering and receiving messages/ideas from one party to another party. It is expected that with the same perception and mutual ideas or ideas, organizational development can be realized (Wiyatno dan Muhyadi, 2013)¹³.

(c) Hypotheses 5, 6, 7 and 8

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.867 ^a	.752	.745	10,194

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Development, Managerial Competence, Communications Interpersonal, Innovative Behavior

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43214,037	4	10803,509	103,969	,000 ^b
	Residual	14235,738	137	103,910		
	Total	57449,775	141			

a. Dependent Variable: Principal Performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Development, Managerial Competence, Communications Interpersonal, Innovative Behavior

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19,402	4,528		4,285	,000
	Perilaku Inovatif	,348	,100	,237	3,480	,001
	Komunikasi Interpersonal	,340	,079	,294	4,275	,000
	Kompetensi Manajerial	,110	,031	,253	3,519	,001
	Pengembangan Organisasi	,213	,066	,205	3,241	,001

a. Dependent Variable: Principal Performance

5) Analysis of the effect of innovative behavior through managerial competence on the performance of primary school principals.

It is known that the direct effect of innovative behavior on primary school principals' performance is 0.237. while the indirect effect of innovative behavior through managerial competence on the performance of SD principals is the multiplication between the beta value of innovative behavior towards managerial competence and the beta value of managerial competence on the performance of SD principals: $0.421 \times 0.253 = 0.1065$ then the total effect of the innovative

behavior given to the performance of the elementary school head is the direct effect coupled with the indirect effect namely: $0.237 + 0.1065 = 0.343$. Based on the calculation results above it is known that the value of direct influence is 0.237 and the indirect effect is 0.106 which means that the value of direct influence is greater than the value of indirect effect, this result shows that indirectly innovative behavior through managerial competence does not influence the performance of the head school. Based on the results of testing the fifth hypothesis obtained a significant path coefficient between Innovative Behavior and Performance, namely: $\rho_{51} = 0.237$,

Furthermore, based on the results of the calculation of proportional influence obtained direct influence of Innovative Behavior on Performance a by 0.237. Thus Innovative Behavior has a direct positive effect on performance, of which 23.70% of performance changes can be determined by Innovative Behavior. Hadi (2015)⁴ in his research stated the importance of innovative behavior to get attention to improve performance. Furthermore, Chayani (2013)² argues that innovative behavior refers to the acceptance of innovation and creative attitudes so that the process of changing attitudes from traditional to modern, or from attitudes that have not progressed to attitudes that have been developed. The results of Rosalina research (2013)¹⁰ suggest that innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the performance of SMK heads in the city of Padang. The results of Seprina research (2013)¹¹ suggest that the performance of principals of private SMP in East Padang is positively and directly influenced by perceptions about innovative attitudes.

6) Analysis of the influence of interpersonal communication through managerial competence on the performance of elementary school principals

It is known that the direct influence given by interpersonal communication on SD principal performance is 0.294 while the indirect effect of interpersonal communication through managerial competence on SD head performance is the multiplication of interpersonal communication beta scores on managerial competence with a beta value of managerial competence on SD principal performance namely: $0.405 \times 0.253 = 0.1024$. Then the total effect given by interpersonal communication on the performance of the elementary school head is the direct effect coupled with the indirect effect, namely: $0.294 + 0.1024 = 0.396$. based on the calculation results above obtained the value of the direct influence of 0.294 and indirect effect of 0.1024 which means that the value

of indirect influence is smaller than the value of direct influence, these results indicate that indirectly interpersonal communication through managerial competence does not have a significant effect on the performance of the head elementary school in Labuhanbatu Regency. Based on the results of the sixth hypothesis testing obtained a significant path coefficient between Interpersonal Communication with Performance, namely: $\rho_{52} = 0.294$, then based on the results of the calculation of proportional influence obtained direct influence of interpersonal communication on performance of 0.294. Thus interpersonal communication has a direct positive effect on performance, which amounted to 29.40% changes in performance can be determined by interpersonal communication. Based on the results of the sixth hypothesis testing obtained a significant path coefficient between interpersonal communication with performance. Likewise, the interpersonal communication of the principal in his daily life turns out to affect performance. Thus interpersonal communication from the principal with people who are involved with their daily tasks and responsibilities needs to be intensified in line with what Corbin & White states. Based on the results of research conducted by Lalropui states that interpersonal communication in recent years places the highest as an important condition for successful work performance in organizations (Jamali, 2013)⁵. Good interpersonal communication skills are very important for employees to make a successful organization. Syarif (2011)¹² added that school principals need to have the ability to communicate important matters to create a conducive and dynamic working atmosphere.

7) Analysis of the effect of innovative behavior through organizational development on the performance of elementary school principals

It is known that the direct effect of the innovative behavior on the performance of SD principals is 0.237. while the indirect

effect of innovative behavior through organizational development on the performance of SD principals is the multiplication between the beta value of innovative behavior towards organizational development and the beta value of organizational development on SD performance, namely: $0.324 \times 0.205 = 0.066$. then the total effect of the innovative behavior given to the performance of the elementary school head is the direct effect coupled with the indirect effect namely: $0.237 + 0.066 = 0.303$. based on the calculation results above obtained the value of the direct influence of 0.066 and indirect effect of 0.237 which means that the value of indirect influence is smaller than the value of direct influence, these results indicate that indirectly innovative behavior through organizational development has no significant effect on the performance of the head elementary school in Labuhanbatu Regency. Innovative behavior influences performance, Hadi (2015)⁴ in his research stated the importance of innovative behavior gets attention to improving performance. Furthermore, Rosalina (2013)¹⁰ suggests that innovative behavior refers to the acceptance of innovation and creative attitude so that the process of changing attitudes from traditional to modern, or from the cycle: not yet advanced to an attitude that has advanced. Innovation according to West (Chayani, 2013)² is the deliberate introduction and application in a job, work team or organization, from ideas, processes, products, or new procedures for a job, work team, or the organization to benefit the work, work team or organization. Another definition of innovative behavior stated by Kleysen and Street (Winaryati, 2012)¹⁴, namely individual actions that lead to the emergence, introduction, and application of something new and beneficial include the development of new product ideas, or technologies, changes in administrative procedures that aim to improve work relations or the application of new ideas or technologies to work significant processes. Based on the seventh hypothesis testing

results obtained a significant path coefficient between Managerial Competence and Performance, namely: $\rho_{53} = 0.253$, Furthermore, based on the calculation of proportional effect obtained direct influence of Managerial Competence on Performance of 0, 253. Thus Managerial Competence has a direct positive effect on Performance, where 25.30% of changes in performance can be determined by Managerial Competence. The role of the Principal's Managerial Competency factor has also been found to be instrumental in determining the performance of the principal. Managerial competence principals influence the performance of the head of school. This is consistent with the results of the research of Muhammad Ihsan Panata which shows that there is a positive effect of managerial competence on the performance of primary school principals at 62.5% in the banjarsari sub-district. Research conducted by Nani Hanifah suggests that there is a direct influence of leadership on the performance of the Principal of the Public Elementary School in Kramat Jati District, East Jakarta. The results of the research by Budi Suhardiman suggest that competence has a very high influence on the performance of the principals of state junior high schools in Garut regency. The results of Sopanto Adrianto's research Managerial Skill directly influence the performance of the Principal of Public Elementary Schools in the Central Jakarta area by 48.30% with a path coefficient of 0.695 (Rahman, 2015)⁹. To improve performance, one of them is to improve the principal's managerial competence because principals as managers are required to be able to develop school plans at various levels of planning; developing school organizations in accordance with needs; lead the school in the context of optimally utilizing school resources; manage school change and development towards effective learning organizations; creating a school culture and climate that is conducive and innovative for student learning; manage teachers and staff in the context of utilizing human resources

optimally; manage school facilities and infrastructure in the context of efficient utilization; manage school and community relations in the context of seeking support for ideas, learning resources, and school financing; manage students in the context of acceptance of new students, and placement and capacity building of students; manage curriculum development and learning activities in accordance with the direction and objectives of national education; manage school finances in accordance with the principles of accountable, transparent and efficient management; managing school administration in supporting the achievement of school goals; managing school-specific service units in supporting learning activities and student activities at school; managing school information systems in supporting program preparation and decision making; utilize information technology advancements to improve learning and school management; monitoring, evaluating, and reporting the implementation of school activities programs with appropriate procedures, and planning for follow-up (Manap et al, 2010)⁷.

Likewise, the interpersonal communication of the principal in his daily life turns out to affect Managerial Competence and performance. Thus, interpersonal communication from the principal with people involved with their daily tasks and responsibilities needs to be intensified in line with what Corbin & White states. Interpersonal communication compared with other types of communication is considered more effective in changing attitudes, beliefs, opinions, and communicant behavior. Because this communication takes place face to face because with that communication there is personal contact that is the personal communicator touching the communicant person. When delivering a message, feedback takes place instantaneously, the communicant's response to the message conveyed can be known through facial expressions and speaking style. It is expected that both superiors and

subordinates will be willing to support work programs that have been prepared by the school principal and will ultimately improve their performance.

8) Analysis of the influence of interpersonal communication through organizational development on the performance of elementary school principals

It is known that the direct effect of interpersonal communication on the performance of SD principals is 0.294, while the indirect effect of interpersonal communication through organizational development on the performance of SD principals is the multiplication between the beta value of interpersonal communication on organizational development and the beta value of organizational development on SD performance, namely: $0.411 \times 0.205 = 0.084$. Then the total effect given by interpersonal communication on the performance of SD principals is the direct effect coupled with the indirect effect namely: $0.294 + 0.084 = 0.378$. based on the calculation results above obtained the value of the direct influence of 0.294 and indirect effect of 0.084 which means that the value of indirect influence is greater than the value of direct influence, these results indicate that indirectly interpersonal communication through organizational development does not have a significant influence on the performance of the head elementary school in Labuhanbatu Regency. Another influential factor is the ability of the principal to carry out organizational development, in this case, is the school. The Principal's role in school development is to be responsible for managerial quality development, while daily operations are the duty of all school personnel and related stakeholders. Organizational development is important to do because it leads to an increase in organizational effectiveness to strive to improve organizational capabilities in adjusting to changes in the environment as well as changes in the behavior of members of the organization (Yudani, 2013)¹⁵. An effective organization will

make planned changes for the entire device and system, structure, culture, group dynamics, quality of human resources, business strategy, and so forth. Various studies suggest that organizational development influences performance.

CONCLUSION

From the research results it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the managerial competence of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the innovative behavior of elementary school principals, the better managerial competence of SD principals in Labuhanbatu Regency.
- 2) Innovative behavior has a direct positive effect on the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the higher the level of innovative behavior, the better the performance of SD heads in Labuhanbatu Regency.
- 3) Innovative behavior has a positive and positive influence on the development of elementary school organization leaders in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, high-level innovative behavior, high-level development of SD head organizations in Labuhanbatu Regency.
- 4) Interpersonal communication has a positive direct effect on the managerial competence of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better the interpersonal communication, the better the managerial competence of the head of SD in Labuhanbatu District.
- 5) Interpersonal communication has a positive and positive effect on the performance of elementary school teachers in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better interpersonal communication, the better the head of SD in Labuhanbatu District.
- 6) Interpersonal communication has a positive positive effect on the development of the organization of the

head of elementary school in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better interpersonal communication, the better the development of the SD head organization in the Port of Batu District.

- 7) Managerial competence has a direct positive effect on the performance of elementary school principals in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the better managerial competency of the SD Principal, the better the SD head in Labuhanbatu District.
- 8) Organizational development has a positive direct effect on the performance of elementary school heads in Labuhanbatu Regency. In other words, the high level of organizational development skills of SD principals is improving the head of SD in Labuhanbatu Regency.

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